

OBESITY AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH METABOLIC SYNDROME IN ADOLESCENTS 10–18 YEARS OLD IN KHORESM REGION

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To determine the prevalence of obesity and its association with metabolic syndrome in adolescents aged 10 - 18 years, as well as to assess risk factors

ABSTRACT

In recent years, the incidence of obesity among children and adolescents has been increasing significantly worldwide, as well as in Uzbekistan. Obesity in adolescents not only negatively affects physical development, but also increases the risk of cardiovascular diseases, diabetes mellitus, and metabolic syndrome. The limited epidemiological data on the conditions of the Khorezm region make it important to determine the relationship between obesity and metabolic syndrome in this region.

Introduction

In recent years, the incidence of obesity among children and adolescents has been increasing significantly worldwide, as well as in Uzbekistan. Obesity in adolescents not only negatively affects physical development, but also increases the risk of cardiovascular diseases, diabetes mellitus, and metabolic syndrome. The limited epidemiological data on the conditions of the Khorezm region make it important to determine the relationship between obesity and metabolic syndrome in this region.

To determine the prevalence of obesity and its association with metabolic syndrome in adolescents aged 10 - 18 years, as well as to assess risk factors.

To determine the prevalence of obesity among adolescents in the Khorezm region. To assess the status of metabolic syndrome components (blood pressure, glucose levels, lipid profile, abdominal obesity) in adolescents. To analyze the relationship between obesity and metabolic syndrome components. To identify risk factors for obesity and metabolic syndrome (i.e., gender, age, physical activity, eating habits).

Results and discussion

The study included 500 adolescents aged 10 - 18 years. Of these, 18% were found to be obese and 22% were overweight. The prevalence of metabolic syndrome among obese adolescents was 12%, compared to only 2% among normal-weight adolescents. There was a significant correlation between obesity and metabolic syndrome ($r = 0.45$; $p < 0.01$). The most common components of metabolic syndrome were: abdominal obesity (80%), high triglycerides (45%), low HDL cholesterol (40%), and hypertension (35%). Gender differences: obesity and metabolic syndrome were observed almost equally in boys and girls. Obesity in adolescents is a major risk factor for the development of metabolic syndrome. The results of the study are consistent with international studies. The obesity rate in the Khorezm region is similar to the national average, but the high prevalence of metabolic syndrome components

indicates the need for early prevention measures. Eating habits and lack of physical activity play a significant role in the development of metabolic syndrome.

Conclusion

Obesity is widespread among adolescents in the Khorezm region and is directly related to metabolic syndrome. The most common components of metabolic syndrome are abdominal obesity and lipid changes. Early preventive measures, healthy eating, and physical activity promotion are necessary to reduce the risk of obesity and metabolic syndrome.

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